

Journey of both amusement and reflection

Sylvester ReddyReader4

October 1, 2024

[BOOK REVIEW]

 Sylvester

Delightful!

Reviewed in the United States on October 1, 2024

It is a delightful and thought-provoking compilation that offers readers a unique window into Vietnamese culture, humor, and social commentary. Through 42 witty and satirical fables, the character Kingfisher leads you on a journey of both amusement and reflection. This...

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Helpful

Report

 ReddyReader4

Enjoyable read

Reviewed in the United States on October 3, 2024

I truly enjoyed reading this book. It's full of life lessons, inspirational messages and the beauty in nature, gleaned in short story form. It reminds me of Aesop's fables a little, which I've always loved. Very nice.

Screenshot. Reviews of “*Wild Wise Weird*” [1-2]. Reviewed in the United States on October 1 & 3, 2024.

Review [1]:

It's a delightful and thought-provoking compilation that offers readers a unique window into Vietnamese culture, humor, and social commentary. Through 42 witty and satirical fables, the character Kingfisher leads you on a journey of both amusement and reflection.

This latest edition builds on the original 21 stories, doubling the content and delivering even more sharp observations about life in the bird village. What I loved most is how the collection masterfully balances humor with deeper, humanistic themes, making it both entertaining and meaningful.

Review [2]:

I truly enjoyed reading this book. It's full of life lessons, inspirational messages and the beauty in nature, gleaned in short story form. It reminds me of Aesop's fables a little, which I've always loved. Very nice.

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(* *Note:* This column reprints Sylvester's and Reddy Reader4's reviews [1-2] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [3], with some light edits for clarity and fitting our house style.

References

[1] Sylvester. (2024). Delightful!. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R71IYQY1JVLCZ/>

[2] ReddyReader4. (2024). Enjoyable read. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R12YJ4VMRPCIX8/>

[3] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6>

